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**Development of public administration in the field of national security: global
standards and Ukrainian reality**

It is determined that the development of public administration in the field of national security in Ukraine and worldwide is characterized by the use of institutional approach. Nevertheless, it differs by the degree of its implementation. It is defined that the national legislation needs improvement in the area of specification of the ways of increase of effectiveness of public administration of national security with its institutional forces. The development of democratic civil control in Ukraine was proved, as well as the international co-operation, reasonable budgeting, etc. It was also proved that with regard to its integration goals, it should be implemented based on the best global practices.

Keywords: *public administration, institutional mechanisms, national security, Ukraine, world.*

In 2018, the Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine” was adopted. It has become the result of the requirements of the range of regulations, in particular, the National Security Strategy of Ukraine [3]. These regulations [same] stipulate certain measures from the introduction of planning in the field of national security (in short, medium and long term) to the introduction of regular inspection of the defence and industrial complex of Ukraine. The development of institutional sector of security and

defence forces, particularly the democratic civil control at all stages of national security, is intended to help with this. This innovation indicates the need in comprehensive analysis of institutional sector of Ukraine's security and defence forces, in particular, the fields of activities of such its coordinating entity as community.

The problem of public administration in the context of national security was studied in the scientific works by O. Borysenko, A. Dehtiar, S. Dombrovska, O. Kriukov, P. Pietrzak, V. Sadkovyi, H. Sytnyk, V. Stepanov, K. Sobczyk and others [2; 4–5; 7].

Nevertheless, there is the need in comprehensive analysis of institutional sector of Ukraine's security and defence forces, particularly the fields of development of public administration in the field of national security and democratic civil control. This is our paper *objective*.

Democratic civil control is an innovation of public administration in the field of national security of Ukraine. It is defined as a political standard by the range of authoritative international organizations, like the OSCE, NATO, the EU, and the Council of Europe. Taking the indicated standards into account in Expert Reports “On Internal and External Situation of Ukraine in 2006” and “Ukraine in 2007: Internal and External Situation and Prospects of Development” implemented within the framework of preparation of Ukrainian President's annual messages to Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, the following fundamental areas of provision of effectiveness of public administration in the field of national security were determined.

1. *Accomplishment of formation of the structure of the system of public administration of security sector*. The results of the activities in the indicated field in Ukraine cannot be considered as satisfactory. The fundamental reason for this shall be defined as the absence of complete determination of distribution of functions, powers, responsibility and control in the field of security among the branches of power (see Chapter IV of the Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine”). The absence of this determination of functions causes imbalance of administrative decisions in this

field.

Thus, in 2008, the President of Ukraine submitted to Verkhovna Rada a bill on the reduction of the size of the Armed Forces by 17,000 persons. However, Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine adopted the law that stipulated the reduction of the size of the Armed Forces by 9,000 persons, while in September, the Minister of Defence of Ukraine put forward an initiative to increase their size by 21,000 persons.

2. *Effectiveness of the activities of the State Commission for Reformation of Armed Forces of Ukraine (AF).* This Commission shall clearly define the fields and priorities of reformation of the whole security sector and prepare the projects of relevant governmental decisions. It shall hold meetings at least quarterly. However, European practice in the field of public administration of security sector has no examples of structures similar to this State Commission.

3. *Provision of legislative framework for the main parameters and characteristics of security sector entities in accordance with the incumbent functions and tasks.* The absence of clear and consistent specification of functions and powers of state authorities makes it impossible to provide legislative framework for the parameters and characteristics of security sector entities, which actually makes undetermined the area of coverage and the subject of democratic civil control. For example, the existing legislative functions of Ukrainian Parliament like “determines the fundamentals of national security,” which have a wide and vague interpretation, cover no fundamental issues of national security, including the ones connected with the specific technical equipment for Military organization and with the parameters of operational availability of defence forces. Moreover, without the relevant support, even such specific functions of Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine as the determination of the total size of the AF, Security Service and other military units, just turn into a formal procedure.

4. *Provision of scientific grounds for institutional reforms and state's decisions in security sector.* It has been indicated many times at numerous international

conferences devoted to the problems of security sector reformation that Ukraine has no comprehensive and scientifically grounded picture of security sector and standards, according to which its activities are formed and assessed. Meanwhile, the country is controlled by crisis management, which is based on the policy of ‘short steps.’ However, as the result of this policy that is not based on the grounded strategy, the decisions, which seemed correct firstly, later turned into the serious mistakes. The absence of clear grounding of defence needs resulted particularly in the termination of legislative reduction of the size of the AF and in the suspension of the process of their transition to a contract basis. This has negatively affected the development of the AF and their capability to adequately response to the social and political conflicts in the east of Ukraine (in the period of their beginning, or in 2014).

5. Development and introduction in the practice of public administration of scientifically grounded criteria and methods of phased assessment of the results of functional activities of all structures of security sector. We consider that the attraction of members of the public (experts in the field of national security) shall favour this. Ukraine still has no relevant special developments, which focus attention exactly on the assessment of this field within the framework of its democratization. The absence of these standards causes the appearance of rather subjective assessments of the activities of national security sector’s structures, which have to be controlled at the level of civil control. Even with the implementation of the principle of transparency, certain types of activities in these structures, specific measures and results may be known, but incomprehensible or may be interpreted differently. The absence of proper methodology of assessment of the field of national security is considered by western analysts as a direct challenge to public administration and democratic values.

6. Improvement of legal and regulatory framework of democratic civil control. Since the adoption of the Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine” [3], the previous year actually demonstrated no improvement of the legal and regulatory framework of democratic civil control. NATO experts still note an extremely low

culture of preparation and execution of Ukrainian legislation and even the documents prepared in co-operation with western experts. These documents lack sufficient analysis of the internal situation in Ukraine, defined and clear goals, and adequate implementation programmes. The basic Law of Ukraine “On Democratic Civil Control over Military Organization and Law Enforcement Bodies of the Country” [3] is no exception. The structure of public administration is not indicated in it as the main task of this control so far.

There are still no positive legislative decisions on the following key aspects of this control:

- separation of the fields of activity of the state control agents (including the parliamentary ones) and civil institutions;
- clear regulation of the procedures of administrative, parliamentary and civil control;
- extension of the field of interests of the society outside simple informing about the activities of security sector with possible open discussion and decision-making in the defence sector;
- determination of the role and place of research civil structures of defence orientation and NGOs;
- mechanism of attraction of civil society institutions to the issues of administration of national security system and its control.

A special attention should be paid to the European standard that stipulates that the fundamental documents of national legislation in security sector shall be based on the political consensus of all chief political parties and not only the Government, but also civil society agents. In Ukraine, the level of implementation of this standard is demonstrated by the adoption of the Law of Ukraine “On the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine” and the Regulation of the Government of Ukraine “On the Attraction of the Public to Formation and Implementation of State Policy” [3]. It should be noted that despite the fact that these documents are aimed at the clearer distribution of the

functions of administrative bodies, they have been reviewed repeatedly and, as a result, they have never managed to provide a real democratization of these functions for the intensification of civil control.

7. Increase in effectiveness of parliamentary control. This field was tactically ensured by the intensification of activities of Parliamentary Committee on National Security and Defence. The Committee focused its efforts on the improvement of legal framework for the security sector, on the strengthening of social protection of military personnel. Nevertheless, there are no positive changes in Expert Reports on key issues, which determine the effectiveness of the activities of the Parliament, like the increase in the level of its competence at the expense of the system of informational and analytical support of the activities of Verkhovna Rada and the professional level of MPs; the organization of public dialogue on strategic issues of defence policy in order to increase transparency and to find out public opinion on conceptual issues.

According to the European standards, parliamentary control of security sector will be full only when it takes into account five chief aspects of the activities of defence structure:

- 1) politics;
- 2) personnel;
- 3) finances;
- 4) technical equipment;
- 5) functioning.

Let's take a closer look at some of these aspects. Thus, the first aspect covers the right of the Parliament to consider and approve fundamental laws and regulations: concepts, strategies, programmes. The Law of Ukraine "On Democratic Civil Control..." restricts this rule to the state programmes of reformation and development of the AF and other programmes. However, even this rule is ignored regularly.

The second aspect covers the power of the Parliament to approve the plan of management of the personnel size of all elements of security sector; to approve the

appointment of high military command. These powers in Ukraine are restricted to legislative approval of the personnel size, which usually lacks sufficient scientific ground.

The third aspect is the control of budget at three levels including the clause-by-clause one and the one intended for specific programmes. We agree with the scientists [2; 4; 5] that the new Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine” excessively focuses on the control of the budget in the field of security and defence. However, the issue of correlation of expenditures on this field, which is available in NATO member countries (see Secretary General’s Annual Report: “NATO: fit for the future” [6]) remains open, as well as the size of Ukraine’s expenditures on the development of the indicated field (fig. 1) [4, p. 10].

Fig. 1. Expenditures of NATO and EU member countries in comparison with Ukraine on the field of national security and defence in 2017-2018 (billion US dollars)

Source: made on the grounds of [4; 6]

In addition, the size of major contributions into the functioning of national security in Ukraine during the last 10 years should be indicated (fig. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2. Ukraine's expenditures on the field of national security and defence in 2009-2019 (bln UAH)

Source: made on the grounds of [1]

Taking the size of expenditures on security in NATO member countries (2% of GDP [7]), Ukraine's situation with security budget may be assessed as follows: 1) from 2009 to 2014 – unsatisfactory; 2) from 2015 to present – satisfactory.

Fig. 3. Ukraine's expenditures on the field of national security and defence in 2009-2019 (% of GDP)

* – expected size of % of GDP

Source: made on the grounds of [1]

However, it is necessary to indicate the fact that despite the positive tendency in percent correlation of the size of expenditures on security in Ukraine during the previous years, its money equivalent of security budget expenditures differs significantly from those expenditures, which are made by NATO and EU member countries [6].

Thus, it is important for the Parliament of Ukraine to take a balanced approach to these issues, while it is also necessary to develop Ukraine's international cooperation at the parliamentary, ministerial and other levels. It is necessary to do this to attract this cooperation to joint projects and programmes in the field of national security, in order to obtain international technical assistance, to enter into agreements within the frameworks of trust funds, etc. We agree with the scientists [4; 5] that the implementation of these measures is caused by the fact that it is difficult for Ukraine to provide material and financial improvement of public administration in the field of national security without assistance.

It should be noted that in the European practice, a special attention is paid to the issue of competence of a parliament, as without the competence of its members, without the close cooperation with defence ministry, an appropriate exercise of power by the parliament and an effective planning in national security, defence and law enforcement agencies is impossible.

8. *Accuracy of the system of periodic open reporting and personal responsibility of high state officials for the quality and implementation of decisions made in the field of national security.* In the European practice, this system of accountability is considered simultaneously with the distribution of responsibility for the performed actions as a foundation for the performance of official functions, and as a precondition for the best possible separation of powers among the institutions in the field of security and defence. It is a European rule that the security, defence and law enforcement

ministers are reporting to Prime Minister and parliament. If the parliament is not satisfied with the situation in the structures of security sector, it may dismiss the top management or specific ministers. In Ukrainian reality, despite the President's annual message and the periodic reporting of security, defence and law enforcement agencies, there are still no signs of bringing them to personal liability. As a result of this, there is a permanent crisis in the security and defence sector.

9. Transparency of conceptual decision-making processes in the field of security.

In the EU, publications on the security issues, an annual defence budget, an annual report on the state of defence and Armed Forces are the specially prepared open documents. They are the results of studies, political consultations and public discussions, and shall be approved by the parliament and government as the materials aimed at provision of information to the society. However, in Ukraine, the creation of practical mechanisms, with the help of which it could be possible to ensure the necessary level of defence policy issues interpretation and provision of information to the society, the creation of conditions for public opinion formation and its influence on the state's fundamental decision-making is still a problem area.

10. Creation of mechanisms aimed at the attraction of civil society institutions to the practice of formation of state policy in the field of national security. In this aspect, Ukrainian practice is restricted to the formation of civil non-governmental advisory councils under the security sector structures' management, rare attraction of civil experts and non-governmental analytical centres to discussions of some issues of defence policy. In this aspect, European practice shows that the activities of NGOs in the system of control need the support of the parliament, mainly through the establishment of effective legislative environment.

Thus, based on the analysis of the legislation, as well as the informational and analytical materials of Ukraine and the EU member countries in the field of national security, it was defined that the increasing use of institutional approach is peculiar to them. However, the degree of introduction of this approach is different. It was

determined that the national legislation needs improvement in the part of specification of its conceptual framework, as well as the ways of increase in effectiveness of public administration of national security with its institutional forces. In this context, the development of democratic civil control in Ukraine was grounded, as well as international co-operation, reasonable budgeting, etc. It was proved that with regard to its integration goals, it should be implemented based on the best European practices.

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